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CESAR1 solvent degradation in pilot and laboratory scale

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Abstract

The non-proprietary CESAR1 amine blend has been widely studied for use as a solvent for post-combustion CO₂ capture.¹⁻⁵ Despite of its relative popularity in the solvent market, there are still many knowledge gaps connected to the stability of CESAR1. The mixture of 2-amino-2-methyl propanol (AMP, CAS 124-68-5) and piperazine (PZ, CAS 110-85-0) is known to be much more stable than ethanolamine (MEA, CAS 141-43-5), both under oxidising conditions, thermal stress, and at the cyclic conditions in the CO₂ capture plant. Despite of solvent degradation being low compared to other solvents, degradation phenomena need to be fully understood before a solvent can be safely implemented for large or full-scale CO₂ capture from industrial sources, to fully comprehend potential environmental and operational impacts, and ensure safety for operators and neighbours.

In this work, we aim to fully elucidate the degradation patterns of CESAR1 at industry relevant conditions. Oxidative and thermal degradation experiments with AMP, PZ, and CESAR1 will be performed, and their degradation patterns and chemistry will be compared to solvent samples from industrial operations. In the Norwegian CCS research centre (NCCS) and the HEU project AURORA, new CESAR1 degradation compounds have been identified and quantified. Currently, LC-MSMS methods for the quantification of more than 30 CESAR1 specific degradation compounds are available at SINTEF, in addition to generic amine degradation compounds such as carboxylates, aldehydes, and alkylamines. A total nitrogen (TN) analysis was also performed to assess whether all nitrogen containing degradation compounds have been identified in the used solvent.

A CESAR1 solvent sample from a pilot scale operation at the Technology Centre Mongstad (TCM) is currently partly characterised. Figure 1 shows the concentrations of 29 of the components present in the used solvent. In addition to these, acetone (148 mg/L), formaldehyde (89 mg/L), and acetaldehyde (4 mg/L), as well as the solvent amines AMP (264 g/kg) and PZ (94 g/kg) were also quantified. Furthermore, 20 other compounds were also included in the analysis of the sample, but none of them were found above their respective limits of quantification (0.1-1 mg/kg, depending on compound).

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Figure 1: Concentrations of degradation compounds in CESAR1 solvent after ended operation at TCM.

The majority of the quantified compounds, like HMeGly (CAS 1154902-47-2), TMOX (CAS 15833-17-7), DMOZD (CAS 26654-39-7), EDA (CAS 107-15-3), and AEAAC (CAS 24123-14-6) seem to originate from oxidative degradation reactions. Oxidative degradation experiments with the single amines, as well as the mixture, it will be possible to establish which mechanistic routes are more likely to take place. The high concentration of methyl-AMP (CAS 27646-80-6) is likely due to its presence as a contaminant in fresh AMP, as a side product of AMP synthesis. As expected, there is also a significant presence of nitrosamines in the used CESAR1 solvent, mainly that originating from PZ nitrosation, MNPZ (CAS 5632-47-3), but also nitroso-*N*-methyl-AMP (CAS 27646-81-7). Smaller amounts of the corresponding nitramines, PZ-NO₂ (CAS 42499-41-2), and AMP-NO₂ (CAS 1239666-60-4) are also present in the solvent. TN analysis of the same solvent sample as was characterised with LC-MSMS, indicates that all, or nearly all nitrogen containing degradation compounds have been identified in the used CESAR1 sample from TCM.

At the GHGT-17 conference we will present some degradation compounds that have not been quantified in CESAR1 previously (or other amine solvents), including the ones depicted in Table 1. In addition, results from purely oxidative and thermal degradation experiments are compared with the TCM operational sample to identify the conditions at which each compound is formed. The findings will aid in the understanding, controlling, and mitigation of degradation during large-scale CO₂ capture operations with the CESAR1 solvent.

Table 1: Identified degradation compounds that have previously not been quantified in CESARI, PZ, or AMP.

Abbrev.	Name	Structure	CAS-number
AAEA	2-amino- <i>N</i> -(2-aminoethyl)-acetamide		84354-31-4
AEAAC	<i>N</i> -(2-aminoethyl)-glycine		24123-14-6
AEAEPZ urea	1-[2-(1-Piperazinyl) ethyl]-2-imidazolidinone		104087-61-8
AEAPZ	<i>N</i> 1-[2-(1-Piperazinyl) ethyl]-1,2-ethanediamine		24028-46-4
AEHA	<i>N</i> -(2-aminoethyl)-2-hydroxyacetamide		83019-76-5
AIBA	2-Aminoisobutyric acid		62-57-7
AMPAMP	2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol		72622-74-3
AMP urea	<i>N,N</i> -bis(2-hydroxy-1,1-dimethylethyl)-urea		162748-76-7
DMPZEA	α,α -Dimethyl-1-piperazineethanamine		1259927-55-3
F-AMP	<i>N</i> -(2-Hydroxy-1,1-dimethylethyl)formamide		682-85-9
HMeGly	<i>N</i> -(2-hydroxy-1,1-dimethylethyl)-Glycine		1154902-47-2
TMOX	3,4,4-trimethyl-2-oxazolidinone		15833-17-7

Keywords: AMP; PZ; stability; oxidative degradation; thermal degradation

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